

IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON FLOOD FORECASTING AND EARLY WARNING SYSTEM IN DISTRICT SWAT, PAKISTAN

Dr. Naveed Jamal^{*1}, Dr. Professor Atta Ur Rehman²

^{*1,2}University of Peshawar

¹naveedjamaluop@yahoo.com

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Naveed Jamal

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18491102>

Received	Accepted	Published
01 November 2025	15 December 2025	29 December 2025

Abstract

Climate change is one the major challenge to flood forecasting and early warning systems (FF&EWS) in the flood prone regions of the world. This study investigates the impacts of climate change on the effectiveness of FF&EWS in District Swat, Pakistan, an area highly vulnerable to glacial melting, erratic rainfall and flash floods. Primary data were collected through questionnaires, interviews, and field observations, complemented by secondary data from hydrological and meteorological records. Findings reveal that climate-induced variations, such as increased glacial meltwater and unpredictable precipitation patterns, have reduced the accuracy of existing forecasting models, leading to delays and inefficiencies in early warning dissemination. Additionally, limited technological infrastructure, inadequate community awareness, and institutional constraints further weaken the system's performance. Climate Change have great impacts on different sectors that weaken flood forecasting and early warning system in Swat District. The study highlights the urgent need for integrating advanced forecasting tools, enhancing local capacity-building, and strengthening community-based early warning mechanisms to improve disaster preparedness. The research analysis shows that structural measures, non- structural measures and strategies are very important to mitigate climate change impacts and enhance the resilience of flood-prone communities in district Swat.

Key words: Climate change, Glacier melting, Flood forecasting, Flood early warning, Flood Hazards.

Introduction

Globally, the climate change is one the major cause of hydro-meteorological disasters (Butts, M., et al., 2006). The risk of natural disaster are also increasing due to human intervention in natural environment (Bronstert, 2003; Hunter et al. 2005). Flood is one of the natural disasters, that is cause by climate change and human activites (Chubey, 2004). Climate change is increasingly recognized as a key driver of hydrological extremes, including more frequent and intense flooding events across the globe (Shahbaz, 2024). In Pakistan, rising temperatures have altered precipitation patterns and accelerated glacial melt in the

Himalaya-Hindukush region, contributing to increased flood risk during the monsoon season. Climate change has intensified extreme precipitation and runoff, challenging traditional flood management approaches that rely on historical hydro-meteorological patterns for prediction and preparedness (Shrestha, 2019). These shifts underscore the necessity of improving flood forecasting models and integrating climate projections into risk assessment frameworks, particularly in vulnerable mountainous regions such as Swat District (Khosro, 2025).

Effective flood forecasting and early warning systems (FF&EWS) are vital components of

climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction strategies, enabling agencies and communities to anticipate flood events and take timely action to reduce loss of life and property (Salgado, 2025). However, district Swat existing system have historically been limited by inadequate data networks, outdated forecasting tools, and insufficient integration of hydro-meteorological variables influenced by climate change (Tellman, 2021). As a response to these challenges, new technologies such as AI-driven flood forecasting and early warning mechanisms have been introduced in parts of the region to improve detection of rising water levels and provide alerts well ahead of flood peaks (Qammar, 2024). Such innovations illustrates the efforts to harness advanced data analytics and remote sensing to overcome the limitations of traditional forecasting under changing climate conditions (Yousafzai, 2024). Pakistan is greatly affected by the hydrological and meteorological disasters in history (Rahman and Shaw, 2015). The devastating flood of 2010 was the history worst flood that caused almost two-thousand fatalities, injuries, sources of livelihood earnings, infrastructures and millions of people were displaced (Mustafa & Wrathall, 2011). Till, 2005 the government rely on reactive approaches, but after the earthquake of 2005 a paradigm shift occurred and the approach was changed from reactive to proactive approach. To mitigate natural disasters Pakistan, the government of Pakistan has established NDMA in 2010 to mitigate the hydrological and metrological disasters (Rahman and Shaw, 2015). For this purpose Pakistan adopted different structural and non-structural measures in order to minimize the impacts of these natural disasters. In present scenario flood forecasting and early warning system is one of the important non-structural measures to reduced the flood risk in the flood prone areas of Pakistan.

In the climate change perspective the role of flood forecasting and early warning system is very important due to the intensity and magnitude of flood events. (Rahman and Khan, 2011). District Swat is located in the Northern part of Pakistan, which is posing a serious threat to flood, due to climate change. In order to understand the effect of climate change on Kalam glacier an investigation study has been

conducted to assess the impact of climate change forecast in early warning system in order to protect the natural environment and livelihood of people living in district Swat. The effectiveness of flood forecasting and early warning system varies from place to place, due to the advance radar system install in that particular area and the radar coverage. That's why this is this study is an important attempt to find out the impacts of climate change on flood forecasting and early warning system in the study area.

The study area

This research was carried out in district Swat located in the northern part of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. District Swat is part of the eastern Hindukush ranges where the elevation varies from 500 m to over 4,000 m above sea level. It is located between 34°34' to 35°55' N latitude and from 72°10' to 72°50' E longitude. The total area of district Swat is approximately 5,337 km² as shown in Figure, 1. According to Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2017), the population of district Swat was 2,308,624 and distributed with an average population density of 432 persons per square kilometer (GoP, 2017). The study area is mainly defined by the drainage basin of river Swat and its tributaries. There are several snow covered, mountain peaks having 4,000 m elevation above sea level (Khan, 2006).

In rainy season, the heavy discharge in Swat river and its tributaries overflow the natural levees and causes damages to infrastructure, standing crops, sources of livelihood earnings and human lives as shown in (Rahman and Shaw, 2014). The main focus of this research article is on impacts of climate change on flood forecasting and early warning system. Indicators and variables for the measurement and change differences are selected. In the study area the glaciers melting caused serious damages because of climate change since long time. Similarly due to lack of government authorities attention and meteorological station weak system in the study area no proper data is available regarding the glacier movement, glacier melting and effect of climate change on glacier. No systematic study has been carried out on this problem in the study area.

District Swat is one of the important district, which has been hit by flood in history. The flood of 2010 and 2022 was the worst flood that not only damages human lives, casualties, infrastructures but also damaged natural environment. Similarly flood due to climate change is one of the major threat to human lives and environment. In order to understand the effect of climate change this research has been conducted to assess the impact of climate

change on (FF&EWS) forecast in early warning system in district Swat. The study area is beyond the radar system install by PMD, Islamabad. That's why, this study is an important attempt to find out the impacts of climate change on flood forecasting and early warning system in the study area and to formulate different mitigation strategies to make flood forecasting and early warning system more effective in district Swat, Pakistan.

Figure, 1 The study area (Swat District)

Data and Methods

The data were collected from primary and secondary sources as shown in Figure, 2. This study employed a mixed-methods research design, integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches to ensure a

comprehensive understanding of flood forecasting and early warning systems (FF&EWS) in Swat District. The study area is divided into two zones based on flood characteristics, that is Upper Swat Region and Lower Swat Region (LSR). Upper Swat Region

(USR) is characterized by flash floods, due to its steep slopes, however Lower Swat Region (LSR) is characterized by riverine floods, due to wider floodplains in the down stream areas. The mixed-method approach facilitated triangulation of data sources to validate findings and draw evidence-based conclusions about community perception, institutional efficiency, and indigenous flood forecasting mechanisms.

Primary data collection

Primary data was collected through questionnaire survey, field observation and focused group discussion. The Swat district was divided into two regions based on flood characteristics. The Upper Swat River has flash flood characteristics whereas the lower Swat river has typical river flood. A total of ten communities were surveyed, out of which four was randomly selected from upper region and six from lower region.

A structured questionnaire was designed to assess local perceptions of FF&EWS, indigenous flood indicators, preparedness strategies, and household-level vulnerability. Ten flood-prone communities were selected, comprising four from Upper Swat (flash flood zones) and six from Lower Swat (riverine flood zones). Within each community, 10% of households were surveyed using a random sampling method. FGDs were conducted with elderly residents, community leaders, and key informants, including members of local disaster management committees and community-based

organizations. These discussions helped document local experiences of past floods and traditional forecasting practices.

Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data was collected from various sources. This included official records, reports, and statistical data on floods, infrastructure, and socio-economic indicators. Key institutions consulted were Disaster Management Authorities: District Disaster Management Authority (DDMA) and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Disaster Management Authority (PDMA) for flood-related records. Hydrological and Meteorological data that includes rainfall, temperature, river discharge and warning dissemination data were collected from PMD, Islamabad and Flood Forecasting Division (FFD) and met stations located in district Swat. Administrative and Sectoral data were collected from Deputy Commissioner Office, Irrigation Department, Survey of Pakistan, Agriculture and Forest Departments, Population Census Organization and Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS). This multi-source approach provided a robust data foundation covering flood frequency, severity, impacts on settlements, and institutional response mechanisms. Secondary data about all the selected variables were collected from the related organizations. These organizations are includes DDMA Swat, DDMA Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Flood Forecasting Division, Irrigation Department, Indus River System Authority (IRSA) and Survey of Pakistan.

Figure, 2 Research Framework

Data Analysis and Tools

The collected data was processed and analyzed by using of quantitative and spatial tools. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and statistical tools were employed to analyze survey responses, generate descriptive statistics, and identify trends in community perception and preparedness. Geographic Information System (GIS) tools were used to map flood-prone areas, settlements, infrastructure damages, and hazard zones. GIS also enabled visualization of spatial patterns of flood risk and early warning dissemination pathways. Findings were presented through maps, statistical diagrams, charts, and tables, supported by descriptive narratives to enhance clarity and interpretation. The collected data were analyzed by using different statistical tools and Geographic Information System (GIS). The data was finally the maps, statistical diagrams and tables.

Analysis, Results and Discussion

Impacts of Climate change on Flood Forecasting and Early Warning System

This section discussed different causes of climate change and anthropogenic activities that impacts on flood forecasting and early warning system in the study area as shown in Figure, 3. This brings change in Swat district land pattern. The topography of Swat district is not even. Each area has its own characteristics, while make it vulnerable to flood. In Swat district people dominant over the natural environment and totally utilized the natural environment to fulfill their basic needs. In past the basic needs were limited. All natural hazards such as climatological and hydrological affect the physical environment in the study area. Anthropogenic needs are increased day to day that caused deforestation, precipitation and increased in temperature warming up and degradation of physical environment which effects on glaciers of Swat district. Climate

variability is also one of the major causes of glaciers melting in Swat district. This determines the characteristics of human in the

study area. This makes the atmosphere polluted which finally effect on flood forecasting and early warning system in study area.

Figure, 3 Impacts of Climate Change on Flood Forecasting and Early Warning System

Perception about Natural Hazards in Swat District

In order to determine whether or not the local residents have any idea regarding the natural hazards in Swat district. In order to determine some major natural hazards occurred in the study area questions was asked about major type of natural hazards occurred in the past. The perception analysis of natural hazards in Swat district indicates that floods are the most commonly recognized hazard, with 55% of respondents identifying them as the predominant threat, followed by earthquakes (25%) and rockfalls (20%) (Table 1, Figure 4). This suggests

that local communities are acutely aware of the recurrent flood risks, likely due to their frequent experience with glacial melt-induced river surges and extreme rainfall events. While awareness of earthquakes and rock-falls exists, the prominence of floods in community perception highlights their direct and tangible impact on livelihoods, infrastructure, and settlements. However, despite this awareness, the persistence of flood-related damages points to gaps in preparedness, early warning dissemination, and adaptive response strategies, emphasizing the need for enhanced people-centered flood risk management in the region.

Table 1, Types of Natural Hazards occurring in Swat District

S. No	Natural hazards	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
1.	Flood	27	55 %
2.	Earthquake	9	25 %
3.	Rock falling	7	20 %
Total No of respondents		43	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Figure, 4 Types of Natural Hazards in District Swat

Causes of Glacial Melting in the study area

The objective of this section was to know about the local residents have any idea regarding climate change and other anthropogenic activities that caused glacial melting in district Swat. To know about glacial melting, questions was asked that what they think about the causes of the glacial melting. Among the respondents 53 % of the respondents answered that climate

change is the main cause. About 21 % were in favours of torrential rainfall, 12 % high temperature, 5% answered lightening, 2 % were in favours of deforestation. While 5% were in favours of human encroachment and 2 % answered that the mass movement are the other causes of glaciers melting as shown in Table 2 and Figure, 5.

Table 2, Causes of Glacial Melting in study area

S. No	Causes of Glacial Melting	Percentage of respondents
1.	Climate Change	53 %
2.	Rainfall	21 %
3.	High temperature	12 %
4.	Lightening	5 %
5.	Deforestation	2 %
6.	Human Encroachment	5 %
7.	Mass movement	2 %

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Figure 5, Causes of Glacial Melting in study area

Impacts of Climate Change on Swat district

Swat District, located in the mountainous region of KPK, Pakistan, is highly susceptible to the impacts of climate change due to its dependence on glacial meltwater, agriculture, and forest resources as shown in Figure, 6. Rising temperatures have accelerated glacial melting, altering river flows and increasing the hazard of Glacial Lake Outburst Floods (GLOFs). These climatic changes not only threaten the livelihoods of the local population but also pose serious risks to infrastructure, ecosystems, and long-term development in the district. Climate change has also triggered significant environmental and socio-economic transformations in Swat. Forest degradation, soil erosion, and declining agricultural productivity are becoming increasingly prevalent due to shifting weather conditions and unsustainable land use practices. Moreover, frequent floods and landslides displace communities, forcing them to migrate and leading to unplanned urban expansion in safer low-lying areas. As a result, the combined effects of glacial retreat, extreme weather, and human pressures exacerbate the region's vulnerability, highlighting the urgent need for adaptive strategies and sustainable resource management to safeguard Swat environment and population.

Climate change has had profound impacts on settlements in Swat district, particularly in terms of

vulnerability, spatial distribution, and livelihood security. Accelerated glacial melting and erratic rainfall patterns have increased the frequency and intensity of floods and landslides, forcing communities in high-elevation and flood-prone areas to relocate to safer, lower-lying zones. This climate-induced migration has led to unplanned expansion of settlements, often on agricultural lands or former forest areas, increasing population density in perceived safer areas and disrupting natural drainage systems. Additionally, recurrent climate hazards have damaged infrastructure, housing, and public services, undermining community resilience and increasing exposure to future floods. The shift in settlement patterns, combined with environmental degradation, highlights the urgent need for climate-informed urban planning, flood-resilient housing, and adaptive strategies to protect vulnerable populations in Swat district.

Climate change has significantly affected the road infrastructure in Swat District, increasing both the frequency and severity of damage. Accelerated glacial melt, erratic rainfall, and flash floods have caused frequent washouts, landslides, and erosion along hilly and river-adjacent road networks. Roads in mountainous areas are particularly vulnerable, with slope instability and sedimentation damaging pavements, bridges, and culverts, disrupting

connectivity and transportation. Prolonged precipitation and floods also weaken the structural integrity of roads, leading to higher maintenance costs and frequent closures. The cumulative effect of these climate-induced hazards hampers emergency response, limits access to markets and healthcare, and slows socio-economic development. These findings underscore the need for climate-resilient road design, slope stabilization measures, and integrated watershed management to protect and sustain transportation infrastructure in Swat Valley.

Climate change induced flooding has caused extensive damage to residential settlements in Swat District. To determine whether the local residents have any idea regarding the impacts of climate change questions were asked about climate change and its impacts on different sectors. The analysis

reveals that majority 23 % of respondents agreed that climate change cause the formation of (GLOF), that leads floods. In the upper Swat Region 17% answered that rising global temperatures are causing glaciers to melt at an unprecedented rate, that leads flash flood. While 20% have the views that landslide is natural hazard occurred due to natural climate variability and other human activities. About 9% respondents were the views that deforestation exacerbate flood impacts, 14% answered that climate change caused heavy rainfall in the upper and lower Swat Region that leads floods which finally impacts on Flood Forecasting and early warning. However, 17 % answered that climate change have impacts on settlements, that's why people living in district Swat are planning to migrate as shown in Table. 3, and Figure, 6.

Table 3, Impacts of Climate Change on Swat District

S. No	Impacts of Climate Change	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
1.	GLOF	10	23%
2.	Flash flood	7	17%
3.	Landslide	9	20%
4.	Deforestation	4	9%
5.	Rainfall	6	14%
6.	Settlements	7	17%
Total respondents		43	100%

Source: (Field survey, 2022)

Figure, 6 Impacts of Climate Change on Swat District

Discussion

The results clearly indicates that climate change, coupled with intensified anthropogenic

activities, has significantly altered the environmental and hydrological conditions of Swat District finally the leading causes of

natural events (Figure 4). The district non-uniform topography, comprising mountainous glaciated regions and low-lying plains, responds differently to climatic stressors. Rising temperatures caused by atmospheric pollution, deforestation and increased human pressure have accelerated glacial melting in the upper catchments. This accelerated melt has increased variability in river discharge, making flood behavior less predictable and reducing the accuracy of conventional flood forecasting models that rely on historical hydrological trends. Furthermore, increased deforestation and land exploitation have degraded the physical environment, increasing surface runoff and sedimentation in river channels. These changes complicate flood forecasting and early warning systems by altering flood timing, magnitude, and duration. The findings suggest that climate-induced environmental degradation directly weakens the effectiveness of existing early warning mechanisms in Swat, which are not fully adapted to rapidly changing climatic and land-use conditions.

Climate change has significantly altered the hydrological regime of District Swat, Pakistan, is one of the major challenge for effective FF&EWS. The increasing variability in precipitation patterns and accelerated glacial melting have resulted in more frequent and severe flooding events. Traditional forecasting models, which rely on historical climatic trends, are increasingly inadequate to predict these emerging flood dynamics. This mismatch between climatic shifts and forecasting capacity hampers the timely dissemination of accurate warnings, leaving vulnerable communities exposed to greater risk. The study findings highlights that unpredictable rainfall and rapid glacial outbursts contribute to sudden flood events that makes the existing early warning infrastructure is ill-equipped to handle. Limited accuracy in hydro-meteorological data, outdated equipment, and insufficient integration of modern forecasting technologies further reduce the reliability of FF&EWS. Steep topography of Swat amplifies flash flood risks, making rapid response systems critical. However, climate-induced shifts in weather patterns often outpace the system's operational capacity, creating delays that compromise disaster preparedness and response.

The perception analysis (Table 1 and Figure 4) shows that floods are recognized by the majority of respondents (55%) as the most frequent natural hazard in Swat district. This perception reflects the increasing occurrence of flood events driven by glacial melt and extreme rainfall. Although earthquakes (25%) and rockfall (20%) were also identified, floods dominate the hazard profile of the region. This strong recognition of flood risk indicates growing awareness among local communities; however, repeated flood losses suggest that awareness alone is insufficient. The persistence of flood-related damage implies shortcomings in early warning dissemination, response capacity, or community preparedness. These gaps highlighted the need for people-centered flood early warning systems that integrate local knowledge with timely, accessible warnings and preparedness planning.

The results from Table 2 and Figure 5 reveal that 53% of respondents identified climate change as the primary cause of glacial melting in Swat District, followed by torrential rainfall (21%) and high temperature (12%). This perception aligns with scientific evidence linking rising temperatures and precipitation variability to accelerated glacier retreat in mountainous regions. However, relatively fewer respondents identified deforestation (2%) and human encroachment (5%) as contributing factors, indicating limited awareness of indirect anthropogenic impacts on glacial systems.

This knowledge gap is critical because land-use practices such as deforestation and overgrazing influence local microclimates, increase surface temperatures, and destabilize slopes, indirectly accelerating glacial retreat and downstream flooding. The underestimation of these factors may hinder community support for sustainable land management practices that are essential for reducing flood risks and improving forecasting reliability. The findings demonstrate that Swat District is highly vulnerable to climate change due to its reliance on glacial meltwater, agriculture, and forest ecosystems (Figure 6). Rainfall and extreme weather events have disrupted the natural hydrological balance, increasing uncertainty in flood timing and intensity in the study area.

Climate change has also triggered interconnected environmental and socio-

economic impacts, including forest degradation, soil erosion, and declining agricultural productivity. Frequent floods and landslides have displaced communities, forcing migration and unplanned settlement expansion in perceived safer areas. These changes further increase exposure to flood hazards and complicate flood risk assessment and early warning planning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that climate change, combined with increasing anthropogenic pressures has significantly altered the environmental and socio-economic landscape of Swat District, with direct implications for flood forecasting and early warning systems. Rising temperatures, atmospheric pollution, and climate variability have accelerated glacial melting in the upper catchments of Swat District, resulting in irregular river discharge, increased frequency of floods, and heightened uncertainty in flood behaviour. These changing hydrological conditions challenge the accuracy, timeliness and reliability of existing flood forecasting and early warning mechanisms, particularly in a region characterized by complex and non-uniform topography.

Community participation is critical in making early warning systems effective in Swat District. Local residents should be involved in preparedness programs through awareness campaigns, community-based disaster risk management committees, and early warning dissemination networks at the grassroots level. This will build trust in official warnings and ensure timely evacuations and response actions. Utilizing mobile alerts, radio broadcasts, and social media platforms can also help in rapidly communicating warnings to remote and vulnerable areas. Lastly, climate adaptation strategies should be incorporated into long-term planning to reduce the impact of floods in Swat. This includes reinforcing flood-prone infrastructure, implementing riverbank protection measures, and developing climate-resilient housing in high-risk zones. Moreover, continuous research on local climate trends and hydrological patterns should be supported to update and refine forecasting models. By combining technological advancements, institutional reforms, and community

engagement, Swat can build a more resilient and effective flood forecasting and early warning system in the face of climate change.

The analysis reveals that floods are the most dominant natural hazard in Swat District, as identified by the majority of respondents, followed by earthquakes and rock-fall events. Local communities largely recognize climate change as the primary driver of glacial melting, torrential rainfall and rising temperatures. This alignment between community perception and observed climatic trends underscores the growing awareness of climate-induced risks; however, it also highlights the increasing vulnerability of communities whose livelihoods and settlements remain closely linked to climate-sensitive resources.

The findings further demonstrate that climate change has triggered substantial land-use and land-cover changes across Swat District. Agricultural land has declined due to repeated flooding, reduced soil fertility, and water stress, while built-up areas have expanded rapidly as climate-induced migration pushes communities toward perceived safer zones. Simultaneously, forest and pastoral lands have experienced significant degradation due to deforestation, overgrazing, and climate stress, leading to soil erosion, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem instability. These land-use changes exacerbate surface runoff and sedimentation, further complicating flood forecasting efforts.

To improve FF&EWS in District Swat under the influence of climate change, it is essential to adopt advanced forecasting technologies. The integration of satellite-based remote sensing, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), and real-time hydro-meteorological monitoring can enhance the precision of flood prediction models. Additionally, the use of machine learning algorithms can help in analyzing large datasets to generate more accurate and timely forecasts, enabling proactive decision-making and risk mitigation. Institutional strengthening and inter-agency coordination must be prioritized to improve the operational efficiency of FF&EWS. Establishing a centralized disaster management hub equipped with trained personnel and modern equipment can streamline information flow between meteorological departments, local authorities, and emergency responders. Regular training

workshops and simulation exercises should be conducted to improve the technical skills of forecasting staff and ensure effective coordination during emergencies.

Overall, the study highlights that climate change impacts in Swat District are multidimensional, affecting glaciers, hydrology, land use, and livelihoods in an interconnected manner. The environmental degradation and unplanned urban expansion, underline the urgent need to strengthen flood forecasting and early warning systems. Integrating climate change considerations, land-use planning, community awareness, and improved institutional coordination is essential to enhance resilience and reduce future flood risks in order to improve flood forecasting and early warning system more effective in Swat District to mitigate natural events.

References

Bronstert, A. (2003). Floods and climate change: interactions and impacts. *Risk Analysis*, 23(3), 545-557.

Butts, M., et al., (2006). A flood forecasting system: integrating web, GIS and modelling technology. 26th Annual ESRI International User Conference. San Diego, CA: San Diego Convention Center.

Butts, M., Klinting, A., Ivan, M., Larsen, J., Brandt, J., & Price, D. (2006). A flood forecasting system: integrating web, GIS and modelling technology. In 26th Annual ESRI International User Conference. San Diego, CA: San Diego Convention Center.

Chubey, M. S., & Hathout, S. (2004). Integration of RADARSAT and GIS modelling for estimating future Red River flood risk. *Geo Journal*, 59 (3), 237-246.

Demeritt, D., & Nobert, S. (2014). Models of best practice in flood risk communication and management. *Environmental Hazards*, 13(4), 313-328.

Haggett, C. (1998). An integrated approach to flood forecasting and warning in England and Wales. *Water and Environment Journal*, 12(6), 425-432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/DDI.12963>;

JOURNAL:JOURNAL:14724642;W
 GROUP:STRIN G:
 PUBLICATION.

Krausmann, E., & Mushtaq, F. (2008). A qualitative Natech damage scale for the impact of floods on selected industrial facilities. *Natural hazards*, 46 (2), 179-197.

Krzhizhanovskaya, V. V., Shirshov, G. S., Melnikova, N. B., Belleman, R. G., Rusadi, F. I., Broekhuijsen, B. J., ... & Pyayt, A. L. (2011). Flood early warning system: design, implementation and computational modules. *Procedia Computer Science*, 4, 106-115.

Lambrecht, A., et al., (2011). A comparison of glacier melt on debris-covered glaciers in the northern and southern Caucasus. *Cryosphere*, (2011): p. 525-538.

Molinari, D., Menoni, S., & Ballio, F. (2013). Flood early warning systems: knowledge and tools for their critical assessment. WIT Press.

Mustafa, D., & Wrathall, D. (2011). Indus Basin Floods of 2010: Souring of a Faustian Bargain? *Water Alternatives*, 4 (1), 72-85.

Rahman A. (2015). Effectiveness of the Disaster Risk Management System in Pakistan. *The Arab World Geographer*, 18(1-2): 124-138.

Rahman, A. and Shaw, R. (2015). Floods in the Hindukush Region: Causes and Socio-economic Aspects. In Shaw, R. & Nibanupudi, H. K. (Eds.), *Mountain Hazards and Disaster Risk Reduction*, Springer Japan. pp. (33-52).

Rasul, G., et al., (2012). Vulnerability of the Indus delta to climate change in Pakistan. *Pakistan journal of meteorology*, (2012).8(16).

Sadiq, I. K., Yang Hong. Jonathan, J., Muhammad, U. K., and Tom De Groeve., (2014). Multi-Sensor Imaging and Space-Ground Cross-Validation for 2010 Flood along Indus River, Pakistan.

Salgado, M. J. H., Alfonso, L., & Upegui, J. J. V. (2025). Towards integrating community and institutional flood early warning systems: A framework

- applied to an Andean tropical case. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 116, 105126.
- Shahbaz, M., Liaqat, B. Bin, & Ali, A. (2024). Effects of Climate Change on Natural Calamities in Pakistan: A Case Study of 2022 Flood. *Global Regional Review*, IX(III), 54-63. [https://doi.org/10.31703/GRR.2024\(IX-III\).06](https://doi.org/10.31703/GRR.2024(IX-III).06).
- Shaw, R. (2015). Floods in the Hindukush Region: Causes and Socio-Economic Aspects. In *Mountain Hazards and Disaster Risk Reduction* (pp. 33-52). Springer Japan.
- Shrestha, U. B., & Shrestha, B. B. (2019). Climate change amplifies plant invasion hotspots in Nepal. *Diversity and Distributions*, 25(10), 1599-1612.

